

Preparation of Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃ composite membranes with high H₂-permeability

Lei Wei*, Jing Gao

College of Chemistry and Material Science, Langfang Teachers University,
Langfang 065000, PR China

Keywords: Hydrogen separation, Palladium composite membrane, Macroporous ceramic substrate, Surface modification, Hydrogen permeability

With the rapid development and worldwide utilization of hydrogen energy, Pd composite membranes (including Pd-based alloy ones) have attracted more and more attentions and been regarded as one of the most practical function materials for hydrogen separation in many integrated energy systems [1,2]. To further accelerate the application in the fields of hydrogen separation and purification, palladium composite membranes with high permeability towards hydrogen are extremely demanded; meanwhile, ideal hydrogen selectivity is required as well [3,4].

In our present work, macroporous Al₂O₃ tubes were employed as membrane substrate due to their wide market sources, stable chemical properties and low cost. A novel method for substrate surface modification was introduced for the preparation of highly H₂-permeable palladium composite membranes. Homogeneous suspension comprised of TiO₂ nano-particles and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was used for dip-coating treatment on the substrate surface. Afterward, the coated substrate was heated at 600 °C under the atmosphere of nitrogen, resulting in a carbon-doped TiO₂ modified layer on the substrate (i.e., TiO₂-C/Al₂O₃) [5].

For the deposition of palladium membranes on the surface of TiO₂-C/Al₂O₃, electroless plating was performed at room temperature. After completing the deposition, the carbon residue was finally burned out, resulting in a Pd composite membrane denoted as Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃-1. For comparing, TiO₂/Al₂O₃ was achieved through the conventional solid sintering process in air, and the other Pd composite membrane (i.e., Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃-2) was prepared. Membrane performance was evaluated by H₂/N₂ single-gas testing at the temperature in range of 350–450 °C.

Experimental results indicated that hydrogen permeability of Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃-1 was much higher than that of Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃-2 under the same condition, which could attribute to the increase of effective membrane area in permeate side after the elimination of carbon residue. Moreover, Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃-1 had a higher selectivity towards hydrogen, indicating that the novel method for membrane preparation significantly facilitated to the decrease of membrane defects, particularly the role of carbon-doped intermediate layer. Long-term testing indicated that the prepared Pd composite membrane was permeable and stable.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the surface and cross-section of Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃-1 were shown as following. It can be seen that there was no visible pinholes in membrane surface, and average membrane thickness was measured to be 4~5 μm.

Figure (a) and (b): surface and cross-section SEM images of Pd/TiO₂/Al₂O₃-1

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to the financial support by the Research Project of Hebei Education Department, China (BJ2016044) and Natural Science Foundation of Hebei Province, China (B2017408042).

REFERENCES

- [1] Hatlevik Ø, Gade S K, Keeling M K, Thoen P M, Davidson A P, Way J D. Palladium and palladium alloy membranes for hydrogen separation and production: history, fabrication strategies, and current performance. *Separ Purif Tech*, 2010, 73(1): 59–64.
- [2] Yun S, Ted Oyama S. Correlations in palladium membranes for hydrogen separation: a review. *J Membr Sci*, 2011, 375(1–2): 28–45.
- [3] Souleimanova R S, Mukasyan A S, Varma A. Pd membranes formed by electroless plating with osmosis: H₂ permeation studies. *AIChE Journal*, 2002, 48(2): 262–268.
- [4] Tong J, Su L, Haraya K, Suda H. Thin and defect-free Pd-based composite membrane without any interlayer and substrate penetration by a combined organic and inorganic process. *Chem. Comm.* 2006, 1142–1144.
- [5] Wei L, Yu J, Hu X, Huang Y. Facile surface modification of porous stainless steel substrate with TiO₂ intermediate layer for fabrication of H₂-permeable composite palladium membranes. *Separ Sci Tech*, 2016, 51(6): 998–1006.